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of Radiology
BCR 2010

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Alexandroupoli, Greece

Congress Venue
HOTEL ASTIR Alexandroupoli

Organized by:

- Balkan Society of Radiology
- Department of Radiology, University Hospital of Alexandroupoli
Medical School of Thrace, Greece

Secretariat & Official Travel Agency

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Final Programme & Abstracts
Invited Lectures

Friday, October 29th, 2010

08:00 – 09:00 Registration

HALL-A

LECTURE SESSION

09.00-10.30

Liver Imaging

Moderators: **Elmas N. (TR)** – **Drossos Ch. (GR)**

09:00 – 09:20

Focal lesions in non-cirrhotic liver

Buruian M. (RO)

09:20 – 09:40

Focal lesions in cirrhosis

Efremidis S. (GR)

09:40 – 10:00

Diffuse liver diseases

Erturk M. (TR)

10:00 – 10:20

Post-treatment imaging

Secil M. (TR)

Discussion

10:30 – 11:00

Coffee Break

LECTURE SESSION

11:00 – 12:30

Pancreatic Imaging and Intervention

Moderators: **Buruian M. (RO)** – **Gossios K. (GR)**

11:00 – 11:20

Imaging of pancreatitis

Spirovski M. (RS)

11:20 – 11:40

Percutaneous interventions in pancreatitis

Parildar M. (TR)

11:40 – 12:00

Imaging of pancreatic tumors and tumor like conditions

Triantopoulou Ch. (GR)

12:00 – 12:20

Cystic pancreatic tumors

Elmas N. (TR)

Discussion

ORAL PRESENTATION SESSION I

12:45 – 14:15

ABDOMINAL - UROGENITAL

Moderators: **Tsili A. (GR)** – **Goulimari R. (GR)**

DIFFUSION WEIGHTED IMAGING FOR IMAGING FOCAL LIVER LESIONS

Taori K., Disawal A., Sawant A.

Government Medical College, Nagpur, India.

CLINICAL ANSWERS AND UNANSWERED QUESTIONS IN GADOXETIC ACID (PRIMOVI) MR IMAGING OF THE LIVER

Chartampilas E., Valasaki P., Efremidis E.

Clinical Imaging Department, Bioclinic Thessaloniki, Greece.

CYSTIC LESIONS OF THE PANCREAS

Stergiouda T., Dimarelos V., Mavridou Ch., Vachtsevanos N., Tzikos F., Maskalidis Ch., Davidis I., Bintoudi A.

Radiology department, Papageorgiou General Hospital - Thessaloniki

PANCREATIC IMAGING AND INTERVENTION

Moderators: **Buruian M. (RO)**– **Gossios K. (GR)**

IMAGING OF PANCREATITIS

Spirovski M.

Diagnostic Imaging Center, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia.

Imaging of pancreatitis includes variety of imaging techniques, such as ultrasonography, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, endoscopic ultrasound, angiography and ERCP.

Acute pancreatitis is one of the most common conditions where emergent imaging is required. Alcohol abuse and biliary calculus are leading causes of acute pancreatitis. Acute pancreatitis is defined as an acute inflammatory process of the pancreas, with variable involvement of other regional tissues, or remote organ systems. It is classified into mild and severe forms.

In mild form of acute pancreatitis ultrasonography (US) is usually sufficient. In addition, US is accurate in detecting cholelithiasis, and follow up of fluid collection. Morphological changes in mild, or so-called edematous or interstitial pancreatitis are usually subtle, focal or diffuse enlargement of the pancreas and peripancreatic fluid collections might be present.

Contrast enhanced computed tomography (CECT) is standard imaging modality for evaluation of acute pancreatitis and its complications. CECT should be performed in patients with severe pancreatitis who are not improving within 72 hours and in patients with sudden worsening of symptoms during course, such as temperature, pain, vomiting etc. CECT allows complete visualization of the pancreas and retroperitoneum, demonstration of presence and extent of pancreatic necrosis, and depicts all major complications of acute pancreatitis, such as fluid collections, pseudocyst formation, venous thrombosis, pseudoaneurysm, and fistulas. CECT is used for scoring severity of pancreatitis ("Balthazar scoring"), and is useful tool in follow up studies.

Angiography might be sometimes required to diagnose small pseudoaneurysms, although most vascular complications are clearly depicted on CECT and MRI studies.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is sensitive for subtle changes in acute pancreatitis, especially minor peripancreatic inflammatory changes, even in the setting of morphologically normal pancreas [1]. MRI is superior in detection of peripancreatic edema, hemorrhage, and characterization of fluid collections (fig. 1). Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) is noninvasive method in evaluation of biliary and pancreatic ducts.

Chronic pancreatitis is chronic progressive and irreversible inflammatory disease of the pancreas, which results in fibrous destruction of the pancreatic parenchyma. The disease leads to progressive impairment of exocrine and endocrine function. Chronic pancreatitis is acquired either as a complication of repeated attacks of acute pancreatitis, or as a disease distinct from acute pancreatic. Pain is the most common symptom.

In chronic pancreatitis, US can show pancreatic and bile duct alterations, calcifications, and cysts.

Destruction of parenchyma and fibrosis results in atrophy and ductal dilatation, which can be clearly depicted on CECT and MRI (fig. 2). CT is superior in detection of calcifications. MRI is insensitive for calcifications, but MRCP can detect ductal calculus and ductal abnormalities. Secretin-MRCP allows noninvasive evaluation of pancreatic exocrine function, and can detect even small duct abnormalities.

Endoscopic ultrasound (EUS) should be performed in patient with reliably history and loss of exocrine function, if cross-sectional imaging is not diagnostic.

Differentiation of focal chronic pancreatitis or "acute on chronic pancreatitis" and pancreatic carcinoma might be difficult.

Groove pancreatitis is a type of focal chronic pancreatitis that affects the groove between pancreatic head, duodenum and common bile duct. CT and MR show fibrotic mass in the groove. Cystic lesions and thickening of the second portion of the duodenal wall is often seen, as a manifestation of cystic dystrophy of the duodenal wall. Entity is related with groove pancreatitis (fig. 3).

Differentiation of groove pancreatitis and pancreatic carcinoma can be problematic, especially in case of scirous adenocarcinoma, that has significant fibrous component, and exhibits the same postcontrast dynamics as fibrous tissue. On MRCP, abrupt, circumscribed, irregular stenosis, or complete obstruction of the intrapancreatic segment of the common bile duct is seen in case of pancreatic carcinoma, while long and smooth stenosis is often seen in patients with groove pancreatitis [2].

Autoimmune or lymphoplasmocytic sclerosing pancreatitis is a type of chronic pancreatitis caused by an autoimmune mechanism. The pathohistological hallmarks are mixed periductal lymphocytic and plasma cell infiltration and epithelial granulocytic infiltration, that lead to ductal epithelial lesions and venulitis. Obstructive jaundice, loss of weight and diabetes mellitus are main symptoms. Elevation of serum IgG4 and good response to oral corticosteroid therapy are characteristic features. Most of patients present with enlargement of the pancreas, with effacement of lobular countour. Pancreatic parenchyma is usually hypoechoic on US. On CECT decreased enhancement on early phase, and delayed enhancement in the late phase is often seen. On MRI, pancreas might appear slightly hypointense on T1W images and slightly hyperintense on T2W images, with heterogenous diminished postcontrast enhancement during the early phase and delayed enhancement in the late phase. A capsule-like rim of soft tissue might be seen, as a hypodense and hypointense halo around pancreas. The rim exhibits delayed postcontrast enhancement on MRI studies, and is thought to represent inflammatory cell infiltration (fig. 4).

Atypical segmental affection of the pancreas is seen in up to 40% patients, and differentiation to malignancy might be diagnostic challenge in that case [3]. In segmental form of autoimmune pancreatitis, atrophy of the pancreas and significant main pancreatic duct dilatation are usually absent, which favor benign etiology [4].

Autoimmune pancreatitis is systemic disease, other organs might also be involved, such as biliary ducts and kidneys. Retroperitoneal fibrosis, cervical and mediastinal lymphadenomegaly, salivary gland enlargement and pulmonal lesions can also be present.

US, CECT and MRI are currently leading imaging techniques in evaluation of pancreatitis. US is used as an initial tool, it is also useful for gallbladder stones detection and follow up of fluid collections. CECT is most used imaging technique in evaluation of pancreatitis. MR shows better sensitivity and specificity, and if available, can be used as additional modality. EUS should be performed in patients with reliably history for chronic pancreatitis, if cross-sectional imaging is not diagnostic, angiography remains only for cases if small pseudoaneurysm is expected, despite normal CECT and/or MRI finding, and ERCP is used for biliary stones extraction and in cases when MRCP cannot be performed, or is not diagnostic.

Fig. 1: Acute pancreatitis. CECT (a), T2W (b) and arterial dominant phase postcontrast T1W fat-suppressed GRE (c) images. Inflammation and necrosis of the pancreas and mesenteric fat.

Fig. 2: Chronic pancreatitis. CECT (a), coronal reconstruction (b), fat-suppressed HASTE (c), T1W GRE (d) and arterial dominant phase postcontrast T1W fat-suppressed GRE (e) images. Atrophy of the pancreas and dilatation of main pancreatic duct and side branches. Calcifications (a), and intraductal calculus (arrow, c).

Fig. 3: Groove pancreatitis. CECT (a), coronal fat-suppressed HASTE (b), T1W fat-suppressed GRE (c) and arterial dominant phase postcontrast T1W fat-suppressed GRE (d) images. Fibrous mass in the groove (a, c, d), cystic dystrophy of the duodenal wall and common bile duct dilatation (b).

Fig. 4: Autoimmune pancreatitis. T2W (a), T1W GRE (b) and arterial dominant phase postcontrast T1W fat-suppressed GRE (c) images. Enlarged pancreas, inhomogenous and diminished postcontrast enhancement in arterial dominant phase (c), thin rim of inflammatory cell infiltration (arrow, a).

References:

1. Altun E, Elias JJr, Armao D, Vachiranubhap B, Semelka RC. Pancreas. In: Semelka RC, eds. Abdominal-Pelvic MRI. 3rd ed. New Jersey, Wiley-Blackwell, Inc, 2010. p.628.
2. Yu J, Fulcher AS, Turner MA, Halvorsen RA. Normal Anatomy and Disease Processes of the Pancreatoduodenal Groove: Imaging Features. AJR 2004; 183:839-846.
3. Bodily KD, Takahashi N, Fletcher JG, Fidler JL, Hough DM, Kawashima A, Chari ST. Autoimmune Pancreatitis: Pancreatic and Extrapancreatic Imaging Findings. AJR 2009; 192:431-437.
4. Kawamoto S, Siegelman SS, Hruban RH, Fishman EK. Lymphoplasmacytic Sclerosing Pancreatitis (Autoimmune Pancreatitis): Evaluation with Multidetector CT. Radiographics 2008; 28: 157-170.